

PSYCHOLOGICAL TESTING AND ASSESSMENTS

PROJECTIVE TESTS: HISTORY, CONTROVERSY, AND CROSS-CULTURAL ADAPTATION

P. Rupondo

*Africa International University, Department of Psychology, PhD Clinical Psychology,
Clinical Neuropsychology, Nairobi, Kenya*

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the history, contributions, controversies, and cross-cultural application of projective tests in psychological assessment, with a focus on their relevance and adaptation within an African setting. Projective tests, rooted in Freudian psychoanalytic theory and formalized by Lawrence Frank's "projective hypothesis," utilize ambiguous stimuli (such as inkblots and images) to elicit unconscious thoughts, emotions, and personality traits. The history of these techniques traces back to early artistic and association methods by figures like Da Vinci and Galton, culminating in major contributions from Hermann Rorschach (Inkblot Test) and Henry Murray (Thematic Apperception Test, TAT). Despite their value in exploring the unconscious mind and aiding clinical diagnosis, projective tests face significant controversies concerning their reliability, validity, and subjective interpretation. This scrutiny is amplified in cross-cultural contexts, where the use of Western-developed stimuli and norms can lead to cultural bias and misinterpretation. Specifically, within diverse African settings, the application of these tests is challenged by a lack of local norms, the influence of colonial heritage, and the need for cultural relevance. The paper recommends concrete adjustments for the future of projective testing in Africa, including cross-cultural validation studies, indigenization of stimuli, and the integration of local language and indigenous psychological concepts to ensure ethical, meaningful, and valid psychological assessment.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Projective tests are a foundation of psychological assessment, providing insight into the complexities of human cognition, emotion, personality, and behaviour. These tests, which stem from the Freudian psychoanalytic theory, have had a rich historical projection dating back to the 19th century, with key contributions from psychologists such as Hermann Rorschach and Henry Murray, (Bain, Amod & Gericke, 2013). Projective is derived by projection, (Sindhuja and Asokhan, 2016). The writings of Lawrence Frank in his article on projective methods for the study of personality in 1939 brought about the term “projective technique” also known as the “projective hypothesis”, (Frank, 1939). He described the interaction of stimuli-situation for the projection of the “private world” of the individual onto the environment, through organisation of the field, the interpretation of stimuli and reaction to it.

According to Sigmund Freud, a projection is a type of defense mechanism in which a person’s undesirable feelings and self-attributes are renounced and attributed to another, (Rohleder, 2014). An example is, a person who is frequently late and may accuse others of being disorganised to avoid confronting their own procrastination. Projection is the unconscious act of disputing or refusing one’s own traits, thoughts, and emotions and rather attributing them to other people, objects or outside world. Projective tests also known as projective techniques are based on the idea of presenting individuals with ambiguous stimuli to elicit responses that are considered to reveal subconscious aspects of personality, emotions, and behaviour, (Sindhuja, et al, 2016). Psychologists learn about the individual’s psychological traits, attitudes, and behaviors by analysing participants or clients’ responses through tools such as ambiguous stimuli such as inkblots, pictures or images, incomplete sentences, verbal prompts, and some involve roleplay scenarios and drawings. The projective technique is based on the idea that people project their thoughts and feelings onto stimuli, allowing for easier interpretation and a better understanding of their personalities, (Bain, et al, 2013, Sindhuja, et al, 2016, Benoît, & Catherine, 2020).

Though met with critics, scrutiny, and controversy on some elements such as reliability, validity and cultural relevance, Projective tests have evolved over time to encompass a variety of tools and approaches, each designed to reveal different facets of an individual's personality and psychological predisposition (Benoît, et al, 2020). They have also been acknowledged widely and hailed for being valuable tools in the field of psychology (Benoît, et al, 2020, Bain et al 2013). This paper discusses the history of projective tests, notable contributions, debates over their use, and various cultural approaches. It also makes recommendations to improve their relevance in African contexts, highlighting cultural sensitivity and local collaboration.

2. History of projective Tests

Projective tests also known as projective techniques have a long history dating back to the late 16th century, (Benoît, et al, 2020, Bain, et al, 2013, Frank, 1939). The concept has evolved significantly over the years. Projective testing originated with early art, poetry, and word association techniques used by notable figures such as Da Vinci, Freud, Kerner, and Galton, (Dukes, 2024, MacCurdy, 1906, MacCurdy, 1938, Galton, 1879). These pioneers paved the way for the development of more advanced projective tests aimed at assessing personality traits and psychological characteristics (Bain, et al 2013). Projective testing methods in historical records are divided into four major categories namely *association techniques*, *construction techniques*, *expression techniques*, *completion techniques and choice or ordering techniques*, (Das, 2018, Lindsey 1961). To accommodate the earlier work of projective techniques development by Davinci and Kerner the writer of this paper introduces the "*interpretive reflective techniques*: This category incorporates techniques that rely on visual stimuli to evoke responses and interpretations from individuals. The categorical timeline is illustrated in Fig 1.

Fig 1: Major Projective Techniques, Categories, and Timeline of Development:

The concept of projective hypothesis is seen as early as the 16th century in Italy through the work of *Leonardo da Vinci's* notebook (pp. 508 of 1565), which contain descriptions of stimulating the imagination of a painter by observing random patterns, suggesting that individuals could perceive, reflect and interpret various scenes, figures, and movements in ambiguous stimuli. Da Vinci's observation demonstrates the human tendency to find patterns, interpretations, and meaning in randomness, (MacCurdy, 1906, MacCurdy, 1938, Neuringer, 1967)). This concept, similar to pareidolia and apophenia, stimulated the interest of artists and philosophers alike. Da Vinci's note hinted at perceiving movement in accidental forms, a concept foundational to Hermann Rorschach's subsequent inkblot experiment (Watson, 1959, MacCurdy, 1938).

Justinus Kerner, a German doctor and a poet, also contributed to projective tests in 1857. Many decades before Rorschach, he created a series of blotograms known as *kleksographien*. Kerner created photographs by accident with ink blots, (Dukes, 2024). He believed that these images depicted creatures from a hidden world. His art featured terrifying monsters and dark scenes. Kerner's work was distinct from traditional art, and it prompted people to reconsider their perceptions, reflect and interpret the ambiguous images in an introspective way. Pareidolia, or the tendency to see recognizable shapes or patterns in random stimuli, is associated with mental schemas. These inkblot images tap into the viewer's subconscious mind, eliciting interpretations that reveal underlying thoughts, emotions, and beliefs, (Piotrowski, 2022).

In 1879, *Francis Galton*, a founding figure in the field of psychology in Britain, tested the word association method, to measure intelligence. Galton's profound fascination with intellect drove his search for innovative evaluation methods. In Galton's experiments with the Word Association Test (stimulus presentation), participants were shown stimulus words and given a time limitation of four seconds to generate related words (Das, 2018, Lindsey 1961). His work paved the way for the eugenics movement in the United States of America. Galton's experimental studies formed part of the journey of projective techniques, as demonstrated by the word association

method, to assess intelligence. Galton's contributions went beyond intelligence measurement as he helped shape the landscape of experimental psychology. His relentless pursuit of measurements demonstrated his belief in the objective quantifiability of individual differences, (Revelle. 2014). Galton's work not only demonstrated the existence of these differences, but also established a framework for their systematic evaluation.

Emil Kraepelin, a prominent German psychiatrist, made significant contributions to psychology in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries by expanding on Galton's ideologies and experiments. Building on Francis Galton's pioneering work in word association, Kraepelin expanded upon the methodology, particularly in investigating the effects of factors such as fatigue and hunger on cognitive processes (Ahmad, 2017, Silverman, 1990). Kraepelin introduced the association method in 1892 in a clinical setting to study the impact of various physiological and psychological states on cognitive function and assessing individuals experiencing conditions such as fatigue, hunger, and other disruptive symptoms. (Silverman,1990). This methodology attempted to standardize the experimental conditions and attempted to improve the process of investigating the temporal relationship between stimulus presentation and response and understanding human behaviour and cognition.

Carl Jung continued Galton's Word Association by developing the first standardized word association projective test. His insights and contributions helped to bring projective testing techniques to fruition. His word association test, which included 1000 stimulus words, represented a significant advancement in the field, (Mihura, & Meadows, 2018). Participants were asked to respond quickly with the first word that came to mind after hearing each stimulus word. Jung's seminal work from 1910 proposed that individuals with emotional disturbances could be identified by their complexes, such as the inferiority complex. Jung hypothesized that those with such complexes would show significant delays in responding to stimuli during the word association test, as described in his study.

Hermann Rorschach's seminal work "Psychodiagnostics" in 1921 marked a significant advancement in the projective movement of the 1920s. Rorschach introduced the inkblot test, influenced by Jungian and psychoanalytic perspectives. He believed that responses to ambiguous stimuli could reveal unconscious conflicts and essential personality dimensions (Wongvorachan, 2023, Mondal, & Kumar, 2020). Rorschach created ten sets of inkblots for the test. Following Rorschach's pioneering work, research on the Rorschach test surged, with an increase from 38 in the 1920s to over 200 in the 1930s. Early studies focused on scoring the style and structure of responses, later transitioning to a 'sign' approach. Psychologists like Beck and Piotrowski explored associations between Rorschach signs and conditions like schizophrenia and organic brain damage, (Areh, Verkampt & Allan, 2022). Despite critiques, Rorschach test remained highly implemented across various countries in the world.

In the early twentieth century, projective techniques were refined for use in clinical psychology, with a particular emphasis on personality assessment. The Rorschach Inkblot Test, developed by Hermann Rorschach in the 1920s, and the Thematic Apperception Test (TAT), created by Henry Murray and Christiana Morgan in the 1930s, are two of the most well-known projective tests from this time. Projective tests gained popularity in clinical settings, and their applications grew beyond personality assessment. These techniques were adapted in the 1940s for market research to better understand consumer attitudes and preferences, (Das, 2018, Kumar, 2020). However, this transition sparked debate, with concerns raised about tapping into people's subconscious thoughts and emotions for commercial gain.

Szondi's test, developed in Europe in 1937, became popular due to the theory of recessive genes. Szondi proposed that personality traits were inherited via recessive genes, with emotional disorders resulting from having double recessive genes. The test included 48 photographs of mentally ill patients divided into eight categories, (Bergstein, 2017). Test subjects were asked to choose two pictures they liked best and two they disliked the most. Consistent preferences within specific sets of images were interpreted as a sign of possible mental disorders. Despite initial interest, the Szondi

test declined in popularity due to concerns about its validity (Gyöngyösiné, 2010, Bergstein, 2017).

Goodenough and Harris introduced 'expressed drawings' as a supplemental measure of intelligence in the 1930s, paving the way for more standardized projective tests. Buck refined this approach in 1949 when he introduced the House-Tree-Person Test, which required subjects to draw a house, a tree, and a few people, (Baraheni, Heidarabady & Nemati, et al, 2018). This test had a better organized structure than its predecessors. Karen Machover also modified the Goodenough-Harris Test to create the Draw-A-Person Test for personality assessment in 1949. Participants were instructed to draw a man, a woman, and themselves, with a guidebook published to assist in the interpretation of the features presented in the drawings, (Baraheni, et al, 2018).

To summarize, the history of projective tests is marked by significant milestones and contributions from scholars from various disciplines. From Da Vinci and Kerner's early techniques to the pioneering work of Galton, Jung, and Rorschach, projective testing has evolved into a versatile method for assessing personality traits and psychological characteristics. Despite challenges, tests such as the Rorschach Inkblot Test and the Thematic Apperception Test have gained widespread acceptance in clinical psychology. Standardized tests like the House-Tree-Person Test and the Draw-A-Person Test improved projective methods. While some tests raised validity concerns, the overall trajectory of projective testing demonstrates its ongoing relevance in understanding human behaviour and cognition.

3. Contributions of Projective Tests

Projective tests have made notable contributions to the field of psychology, playing a significant role in understanding human behaviour and personality (Bain et al., 2013). Some of the key contributions of projective tests include the Rorschach Inkblot test, Thematic Apperception Test, Draw-A-Person Test and Sentence Completion Test.

Firstly, projective tests such as the Rorschach Inkblot test, and the Thematic Apperception Test have been instrumental in *exploring the unconscious mind* and revealing hidden aspects of individuals' thoughts, emotions, and motivations. By presenting ambiguous stimuli such as images in the Rorschach inkblots, these tests tap into deeper layers of the psyche that may not be accessible through conscious self-report measures, (Rorschach 1921, Murray and Morgan, 1935). Secondly projective tests have contributed to the *assessments of personality*. The unique approach offers a meaningful understanding of individual characteristics that reflect underlying patterns such as emotions, thought content and processes for example the Rosenzweig Picture Frustration Study which measures aggression, (Rosenzweig, Fleming & Clark, 1947).

Projective testing has assisted in the process of *clinical diagnosis and treatment of psychological disorders*. Galton (1879) implemented the first use of assessments in clinical psychology to assess mental states, fatigue, and emotional issues through word association. Rorschach inkblots amongst other psychopathological disorders have been used in responses in schizophrenia and bipolar affective disorder for patients, (Mondal & Kumar, 2021). They have been useful in informing treatment planning through the valuable insight into a person's psychological functioning which helps in the development of tailor-made interventions for mental health improvement, (Benoît, et al 2020).

Projective tests have contributed to the field of *research as a data collection tools* and psychological studies for human behaviour and personality, social interactions, personal development and cognition. Kishimoto, Yamamuro, Iida, et al (2016) conducted a study that aimed to compare Rorschach profiles in young adults with schizophrenia (SZ) and autism spectrum disorder (ASD), given the clinical and biological overlaps between these conditions. The study found that individuals with SZ showed higher stress tolerance, perception distortions, and poorer recognition, while those with ASD exhibited more synthesized responses. This suggests that the Rorschach test may aid in differentiating between SZ and ASD, (Kishimoto, et al, 2016).

Projective techniques have been a valuable contribution as a *therapeutic tool*. The use of these instruments in therapy sessions help to facilitate self-exploration by the client, insight development, and communication between clients and therapists. By engaging in projective tasks, clients can express their thoughts and feelings in a non-directive manner, fostering a deeper understanding of their inner experiences. An example is the study by Kumar et al (2016) which informs on the stress tolerance of schizophrenia and autism spectrum disorder in young adults showing that those with schizophrenia might have more stress tolerance, stronger perception distortions, and simpler and poorer recognition than those with autism spectrum disorder. This conclusion informs the development of therapeutic interventions that assist in the development of stress tolerance for young adults with autism spectrum disorder. Overall, projective tests contribute beyond traditional assessment methods by providing a unique and valuable perspective on human psychology and behaviour. Despite ongoing debates and challenges, projective tests continue to be used in a variety of settings to help us better understand people's personalities and psychological functioning.

4. Controversies Surrounding Projective Tests

Despite their initial popularity, projective tests were called into question in the mid-twentieth century for reliability and validity. This led to a decrease in their use as researchers began to question their scientific validity. The focus shifted to the challenges of accurately interpreting projective test data. However, projective testing has persisted in clinical practice and psychological research, prompting ongoing debates about its efficacy and ethical implications. The history of projective tests shows a dynamic relationship between theoretical advancements, practical implementations, and critical assessments, which influences the evolution of psychological assessment methods over time., (Bain, et al 2013). One of the primary criticisms levelled at projective tests is their *subjective nature*. The interpretation of responses and results to ambiguous stimuli is heavily dependent on the examiner's judgment, which can introduce bias and inconsistency across assessors, for example the Rorschach inkblots as

described in Areh, et al, (2022). The absence of standardized scoring criteria and interpretation guidelines raises questions about the reliability and validity of projective test results. The test creator's lack of norms and did not establish quantitative norms for interpreting test results, leaving it to examiners to determine what constitutes a "good" or "poor" response.

The *validity and reliability* of projective tests are questioned implying that it is neither reliable nor valid as a measure of personality or psychological function. While the test elicits detailed responses from respondents, they do not necessarily imply that it is a valid or reliable measures of their psychological state, therefore test reliability and validity have been cited as a major criticism. (Mondal et al, 2020, Burkeman's 2017). Some studies discovered low reliability for specific scoring systems, with results varying depending on sample size in the Rorschach and TAT. This raised questions about the consistency and accuracy of the test results (Mondal et al, 2020). Despite these debates, projective tests are still used in certain areas of psychology, particularly psychoanalytic and psychodynamic approaches. Researchers and practitioners are still looking for ways to address the limitations and criticisms of projective tests while acknowledging their unique contributions to understanding people's inner worlds and psychological processes.

5. Cultural Perspectives on Projective Tests

Studies have echoed the lack of standardized norms for various cultural contexts, such as in India, raises concerns about the applicability and interpretation of Rorschach test results in diverse populations, (Mondal et al, 2020). According to Benoît, et al (2020), cultural perspectives are crucial in the interpretation of projective tests. Especially the *cultural relevance of test stimuli* in projective assessments. Cultural norms and values and experiences can impact how individuals perceive and respond to ambiguous stimuli. Test administrators should use stimuli that are culturally appropriate. Meaningful and relevant to the test takers

Projective tests lack cultural sensitivity in the interpretation of projective test results, (Benoit et al, 2020). Cultural differences in responses are significant when an ambiguous stimulus is presented to avoid making biased interpretations based on cultural stereotypes. Given the diversity of the test development locations based on Fig 1 in this paper, understanding the cultural context of test takers is critical to accurately interpreting projective test responses, (Mondal et al, 2020, Benoit et al, 2020).

Projective tests should be tailored to the cultural context of the people being evaluated, which includes accurate test material translation, cultural response patterns, and test stimulus relevance. This adaptation enhances the validity and applicability of assessment results. Furthermore, cultural competence among test administrators is essential, which includes understanding cultural backgrounds, recognizing biases, and adapting practices to diverse populations. Culturally competent assessment leads to more accurate interpretations. Integrating cultural perspectives into projective testing encourages a nuanced and sensitive approach to personality assessment, which is critical for validity in diverse cultural contexts.

6. Projective Tests and Their adaptation in an African Settings

The use of psychological assessment tools in some African countries, particularly projective tests, has raised significant concerns about cultural sensitivity, ethical standards, and test validity. Scholars have highlighted the limitations of applying tests developed in Western contexts to the diverse racial and cultural landscape of countries such as post-apartheid South Africa. Limited research is available on projective testing in Africa. Chigevenga, (2016), stated that South Africa is a leading country in psychological practice, testing and research. Chigevenga, (2016) also alluded to the challenges and practices in other African states, indicating a broader perspective on psychological assessment techniques across the continent. Bain et al. (2013) highlighted the historical and current prevalence of projective tests in South African clinical practice. However, their application in this context raises significant concerns about cultural sensitivity, ethical standards, and test validity. Bain et al. (2013) discovered that

projective tests in South Africa lacked cultural diversity and historical context for the population. Tests based on US or European samples were not applicable to all racial and cultural groups in post-apartheid South Africa. This raises concerns about the cultural appropriateness of the measures used, (Scott, 2008). The International Test Commission stressed the importance of ethical testing in the practice of psychology. South African psychologists have expressed concerns about the adequacy of projective test training and the cultural relevance of specific tests. They argue that these tests frequently fail to take into account the broader social and cultural context, including the examinee's cultural background and values, throughout the testing process, (Laher, & Cockcroft, 2013). Furthermore, some of these tests were developed in the 18th and 19th centuries, and their relevance in the modern era, with a different generation responding to different stimuli, is questioned. Moletsane, (2004), emphasized the difficulties of cross-cultural assessment in Africa and stressed the importance of interpreting test results appropriately within distinct cultural contexts.

Scott, (2008) conducted a study in South Africa on how different race groups responded to a modified Thematic Apperception Test (TAT). The test was modified to fit the multiracial sample. The new test (e-TAT) featured characters representing diverse racial backgrounds (black, coloured etc). Results showed no significant differences in protocol length between the original TAT and the modified version. However, black participants scored higher on the modified e-TAT compared to the original, while white participants scored higher on the original TAT. In his paper on reviewing psychological techniques in Africa, Zimbabwean psychologist Chigevenga (2016) discussed the impact of colonial heritage and educational democratization on African psychological assessment techniques. According to the paper, Westernised tools have been introduced in Africa, overshadowing indigenous psychological assessment methods. The review emphasized that Africa inherited Western psychological assessment techniques from the post-colonial era, resulting in Eurocentric assessment practices that may be less applicable in African contexts. The paper suggested that in order to make psychological assessments more relevant in Africa, Western

techniques should be adapted to create African-oriented approaches that take into account the continent's multiculturalism and linguistic diversity.

7. Adjustments of projective tests for future for African settings

Cross-cultural validation studies are critical for ensuring the validity and reliability of projective tests across diverse cultural groups, as emphasised by Benoît et al (2020). These studies compare responses from people from different cultural backgrounds to identify differences in test performance and interpretation. Such research is critical in Africa because of the unique cultural, social, and historical factors that shape people's experiences and perceptions. Important considerations include incorporating culturally relevant symbols, stories, and scenarios into test stimuli, using familiar and accessible language, and ensuring cultural sensitivity and specificity in test design and administration. Additionally, language considerations are critical when administering projective tests in Africa. Test materials should be available in local languages, accurately translated, and culturally appropriate to aid comprehension among test takers. Furthermore, psychologists must be mindful of the continent's cultural diversity, avoiding broad generalizations and recognizing the nuanced differences among African societies. Understanding the impact of historical trauma, community dynamics, spirituality, and trauma in post-conflict settings is critical for carrying out effective and ethical projective assessments across Africa. By incorporating these factors into assessment practices, psychologists can ensure that projective tests are culturally relevant, meaningful, and respectful of people's diverse backgrounds and experiences.

In conclusion, the history of projective tests reflects centuries of evolution in psychological assessment methods, from their inception to modern applications. Despite challenges with reliability, validity, and cultural sensitivity, projective tests remain valuable tools for understanding human behaviour. Moving forward, incorporating cultural perspectives and conducting ongoing research are critical to ensuring the relevance and efficacy of projective tests in diverse populations.

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